

Decoding 'Family' in Manju Kapur's *A Married Woman*

Dr. Anita Powar

The New College, Kolhapur

Corresponding Author – Dr. Anita Powar

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19312161

Abstract:

Indian English Literature shapes and reshapes during the famous and world-wide scenario of globalisation in 1990s decade. Among many writers, Manju Kapur is prominent writer of this scenario. Her writings evolve around Indian traditional family set up with time phases. Kapur's novel *A Married Woman* explores family as institution with prolific dimensions as cooperative institutes, economical systems and as human relations with psychological turmoil. The novel is full of artistic values considering aesthetic, emotional and intellectual elements through the structure of narration. Presentation and considerations of 'family' in literature reflects fine combination of social, economic, cultural and psychological values with artistic superiority.

Keywords: Family, Globalisation, Shape and Reshape, Structure, Literary Values etc.

Indian English Literature is the canon of reflection of social, cultural and psychological as well as political and economic elements with artistic values of literature. Writers, in India from different language separated states, have explored Indian life through their writings in English language. Indian family is the inseparable and structured component in the Indian English Literature. With many formal and informal ways and methods, writers have described 'family' with Indian traditional merits and values. Generally the reflection has been divided into two phases of time: pre-independence and post-independence writings. Pre-independence writings were full of colonial perspectives and post-independence includes number of changes in Indian society. Decades of seventies, eighties and nineties in the twentieth century shape and reshape Indian society with globalisation revolution. In this whole scenario, Indian family undergoes radical changes. Many writers have described the effects

of surrounding economic and political crises through their novels.

Manju Kapur (1948) is the prominent name among Indian English writers who have depicted many shades of family system in their writings. Kapur's novels like *Difficult Daughters* (1998), *Custody* (1984), *The Immigrant* (2008), *Home* (2006), *A Married Woman* (2014) explores Indian family with various perspectives. *A Married Woman* is the complex story of a woman Aastha from Delhi in the globalised period. The novel is construction of various aspects of 'family' life of middle class couple. The novel shows the structure and arrangement of family with its shaping and reshaping elements.

Family in Indian Society during Globalisation:

There was the large spread of education as well as use of developed technology during the period of globalisation in Indian society. Especially in the metropolitan cities young generation was carrier oriented and futuristic.

Such a kind of life style effects on the preparing family after marriage. Aastha in *A Married Woman*, was the well-educated Delhi situated lower middle class girl with hope of good future after her marriage. Her parents were conventional and had little dream about her though she was the only child of them, they felt her as 'load' for them. Her parents were the best example of good couple who carried certain traditions of their community. The generation gap in that period was clear, as Aastha put challenges in front of her parents when she started to love rich Bunty in her teenage and Rohan in her college days. Her parents enforced her marriage with foreign returned so called rich young person Hemant, after her wedding she was happy with him in their early days and it was the expected picture of family as their (both Aastha and Hemant's) parents wanted from them. So here Aastha and Hemant are the carrier of well structure of family from their parents. Moreover certain elements were occurred in their arrangement of family life.

Elements of Arrangements:

To leave parental home by bridegroom and to settle in the in-laws home is the traditional and ideological way of marriage in the Indian society. Previous generation in the groom's home wishes that both husband and wife in the new couple must follow the settled rules of that home and must avail responsibilities for that home. Aastha left her parental house and settled in Hemant's house. Aastha loved and cared Hemant in their early days and also Hemant did. The couple took care of each other with certain negotiations. The couple had two children: a son and a daughter. It was the complete picture of family what every Indian couple want. There was the attachment for each and other in this family. To respect elders and do listen their experiential words is also the parts of responsibilities and both Aastha and Hemant did it very well, as a result

both held super position as Son-in-law and daughter-in-law in their respective families.

Day by day and year by year the picture of Aastha and Hemant's family changed with outer realities and inner expectations of both. The change took place because of certain things which shaped and reshaped their minds.

Shaping and reshaping elements:

As family undergoes radical changes during the ages as certain elements shape and reshape the family. Basically family is the cooperative institute however social changes, economic systems, cultural and political forces as well as psychological turmoil frame the picture of family from the 'time' to the 'time'.

- 1) Family as Cooperative institute: Ecology between husband and wife is the most needed thing in the family which creates family as cooperative institute. Mutual understanding and unity are the required elements in the formation of cooperative family. Aastha and Hemant had the same picture with their family life. Cooperation with each other regarding their children and elders also. The root of strong structure of family lies in the cooperation between husband and wife. Aastha was the 'innocent, unspoilt, simple girl' (41) the perfect girl for the marriage. Her widow mother and his parents were happy with the scenario. However with the issue of economic conditions the picture was going to change.
- 2) System of Economic: Economical needs are counted in the form of earning money. In the Indian family system of economy is more important during and after the age of globalisation. The period introduced the importance of money and materialistic life to Indian society. After developing the means of communications, young

generations in Indian society get more knowledge about the other's lavish life style. Moreover for the sake of 'self' and for children, Indian parents started to get more and more money by working, by doing jobs and business. Aastha's dream of becoming 'teacher' was the part of cultivated materialistic life of her age. After marriage she started to do job of teaching in a school with pure honesty. It was Hemant, who was the main source of bread and butter for their family however thinking from safer side of future she was doing job. Aastha's job was the breaking point of their cooperative institutional family life. She acknowledged surrounded social and political glitches on her own. She was breaker of famous maxim 'woman is earth' (69) by her mother-in-law as her duty was divided into two: her family and her job.

Aastha's relations with family came under certain threats as Aijaz entered in her life. She learnt to handle social relations though she had feeling of love for young and handsome Aijaz. Her economic pursuits with household responsibilities creates absurd psyche. While relating the views of Karl Marks with Sigmund Freud, Terry Eagleton in *Literary Theory: An Introduction* rightly points out: "If Marks looked at the consequences of our need to labour in terms of the social relations, social classes and forms of politics which it entailed, Freud looks at its implications for the psychical life" (132) Considering this view, Aastha and Hemant both became victim of disturbed psychic conditions, however Aastha showed it and Hemant suppressed crisis.

- 3) Psychological Turmoil: As Aastha is the central figure in this novel, writer

explores her psyche through different spans of her life. When she was in adolescent age, she attracted towards same age boys. When she married off, she cultivated tender feelings of love towards her husband. After well brought up of her children and Hemant's busy schedule she felt lonely. Tiny seed of attraction towards young Aijaz and his sudden death developed feeling of 'alienation' deeply in her mind. Unknowingly she had homosexual relations with Aijaz's rebellious wife Pippilika. However she was more confused in that unexpected situations. Aastha ignored her household duties after entry of Pipee in her life. The dimensions of firm family changed over the nights. With radical theory of Freudian psychoanalysis it can be analysed as, Aastha's unconscious was full of images and thoughts about Aijaz and so she felt emotional shelter in his wife that is in the company of Pipee. With these upholds in her and obviously in their family life, distance created in the relations of husband and wife and also in the relations of mother and children. At the end of the novel, after Pipee's leaving her, Aastha again looked towards her family.

Moreover the elements of social, economic and psychological backgrounds, the novel, *A Married Woman* has certain artistic values like its aesthetic depiction of all tender and sweet moments with beautification of events. Intellectual and emotional elements are superbly woven by Kapur in certain incidents. The narration creates empathy about the characters and indicates deep sense of theme. Regarding *A Married Woman*, Sunita Sinha in *Post-Colonial Women Writers* rightly observes Manju Kapur's writing as, "Kapur's preoccupation with

displacement of individual and repression is culturally universal” (166)

Conclusion:

Manju Kapur clearly and boldly points out the hidden aspects of human life while telling about family. Disintegration of family happens with those same elements of integrated family like outer realities of human life and inner struggles of human mind. However the final outcome about the ‘family’ as institution is not the dysfunctions of family but family as power to every individual.

References:

1. Kapur, Manju. *A Married Woman*, Roli Books Pvt. Ltd, New Delhi 110048, 2007.
2. Eagleton, Terry. *Literary Theory: An Introduction*, Blackwell Publishers Ltd, 2003.
3. Eagleton, Terry. *Marxism and Literary Criticism*, DOABA Publications, 2024
4. Sinha, Sunita. *Post-Colonial Women Writers New Perspectives*, ATLANTIC, Publishers and Distributers, 2008.